

TRANSFORMATION OF ONLINE COMMERCE AND DIGITAL ADVERTISING IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES OF KASHKADARYA REGION

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the transformation of online sales and digital advertising tools in industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region. In recent years, the development of digital technologies and the Internet has fundamentally changed the business processes of local industrial enterprises and helped them increase their competitiveness in global markets. Through online sales platforms and digital advertising tools, industrial enterprises are able to offer their products on a global scale. The study pays special attention to the process of transition of industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region to online sales, the effectiveness of digital marketing strategies, and the role of digital advertising in the modernization of the industry. This study analyzes the impact of online sales and digital advertising tools on changes in the marketing activities of the industry and on its export potential. The results provide an opportunity to strengthen the integration of industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region with global markets by introducing digital marketing.

Introduction: The rapid development of digital technologies and the expansion of the ability to connect to the global Internet network have brought about significant changes in many areas of industry, including marketing and sales systems. As a result, enterprises have been forced to use new digital tools and platforms to modernize their activities and increase their competitiveness. In particular, the transformation taking place in the areas of online sales and digital advertising is fundamentally changing the business models and marketing strategies of industrial enterprises. These processes create opportunities to reach a wider audience for products and services, improve marketing efficiency, and strengthen integration with global markets.

Kashkadarya region is distinguished by its industrial potential and natural resources. However, the industrial enterprises of the region, like many other regions, are facing some difficulties in implementing digital transformation. This is due, on the one hand, to the low level of readiness for the use of digital technologies, and on the other hand, to the lack of qualified personnel in digital marketing and e-commerce. At the same time, through the use of online sales and digital advertising tools, industrial enterprises of the Kashkadarya region can successfully sell their products not only in domestic markets, but also on a global scale.

This study examines the transformation of online sales and digital advertising tools in industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region. The study analyzes the impact of digital

technologies on industrial marketing, the role of e-commerce platforms in increasing export potential, as well as the potential of digital advertising in introducing products to global markets. The study also develops suggestions and recommendations for industrial enterprises to improve the effectiveness of digital marketing.

The implementation of online sales and digital advertising in industrial enterprises plays an important role not only in promoting products, but also in introducing the organization's brand to the global market. For enterprises that want to bring their local industry to the international market, it is important to apply digital marketing tools, expand exports, and study the impact of digital advertising. The success of this process can contribute to the economic growth of the region and increase its opportunities for global competition.

Thus, the main goal of the study is to study the transformation of digital marketing and online sales tools in industrial enterprises of the Kashkadarya region, thereby increasing the export potential of industrial enterprises and analyzing the impact of digital advertising on exports.

Analysis of literature on the topic. During the research, a number of scientific and practical sources were studied on the transformation of online sales and digital advertising in industrial enterprises. These sources serve to illuminate the main concepts, theoretical foundations and practical approaches to the topic under study. The literature used is analyzed in the following sections.

There are a number of works on the development of digital marketing and e-commerce. The work "Digital Marketing: Strategy, Implementation, and Practice" by Chaffey D. and Ellis-Chadwick F. emphasizes the effectiveness of digital marketing strategies, their integration with online sales, and the important role they play in developing relationships with global markets. This source reveals the strategic importance of online sales and digital advertising for industrial enterprises and identifies their place in increasing export potential.

Principles of Marketing, by Kotler P. and Armstrong G., explains the fundamental principles of marketing, including the importance of digital marketing for global markets and its role in developing exports. The work contains detailed information on the impact of digital advertising and the opportunities that online sales offer for businesses.

The role of digital advertising and online sales in industrial enterprises Kaplan AM and Haenlein M. in their article "Users of the World, Unite! The Challenges and Opportunities of Social Media" sheds light on the role of social networks in digital marketing and how they create opportunities for industrial enterprises. The study emphasizes the impact of online sales and advertising through social networks on the integration with global markets. This source shows the importance of applying social networks to online sales and marketing strategies for industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region.

Evans D.'s "Digital Marketing: An Hour a Day" shows the practical application of digital marketing campaigns, how to manage them effectively, and how they can help increase online sales. This resource is useful for solving the problems that industrial enterprises face in the process of transitioning to online sales.

The book "Digital Marketing Analytics: The Complete Guide to Analyzing Digital Marketing Campaigns" by Shaw L. and Srinivasan A. on the digital transformation of industry and its export potential shows the effective use of digital marketing analytics tools and how industrial enterprises can increase their export potential by studying digital marketing. The study examines the growth of online sales and the integration of industrial enterprises with global markets through digital marketing analytics tools.

The article "Digital Transformation and its Impact on Export-Oriented Industries" by Ming XY and Ali Z. analyzed the impact of digital transformation on exports and how online trade creates new opportunities for industrial enterprises. The study presents the importance of e-commerce platforms in increasing export potential and new approaches to entering the global market through online trade.

Research on industrial and digital marketing in Kashkadarya region. Research on industrial and digital marketing in Kashkadarya region is very limited, but the available sources help to explore the potential of digital marketing tools in increasing the industrial potential of the region. The readiness of industrial enterprises in the region for online sales and digital advertising tools, the obstacles and opportunities they face in the process of transition to digital transformation are analyzed.

The analysis of the literature used shows that digital marketing and online sales tools provide comprehensive knowledge and practical approaches to strengthening industrial enterprises' connections with global markets, increasing export potential, and utilizing the opportunities of digital advertising. The effective use of digital marketing and the transition to online sales for industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region will have a significant impact on the region's economic growth and integration into the global market.

Research methodology

This study examines the transformation of online sales and digital advertising in industrial enterprises of the Kashkadarya region. The research methodology is based on a mixed approach, which includes a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods. These approaches are suitable for detailed analysis and clarification of various aspects of the study.

The purpose and objectives of the study are to study the transformation of online sales and digital advertising tools in industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region and analyze the impact of this process on the integration of the industry into the global market. The research objectives include:

- Analysis of the current state of online sales and digital advertising in industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region.
- Identify the role of online sales and digital advertising tools in increasing export potential.
- Studying the obstacles and opportunities in the digital transformation process of industrial enterprises.
- Developing proposals for industrial enterprises to implement digital marketing tools.

The following methods are used in the study according to the main research methods:

- Questionnaires and surveys – The current status, level of implementation, and effectiveness of online sales and digital advertising will be studied through surveys and questionnaires conducted with representatives of industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region. The questionnaires will be used to collect information about online sales platforms, digital advertising tools, and their impact on exports.
- Interviews – In-depth interviews with industry managers, marketing specialists, and professionals developing digital marketing strategies will be conducted. These interviews will provide insights into the role of digital advertising and e-commerce in industry, barriers, and successful experiences.
- High-level analysis – Existing economic and statistical data are analyzed to study the marketing activities and online sales systems of industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region. This method helps to study the industrial potential of the region, the impact of digital advertising on exports, and the effectiveness of marketing strategies.
- Comparative analysis – The study compares industrial enterprises and their digital transformation processes in other regions (as well as other countries). This method is useful in determining how the digital transformation of industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region can be studied on a global scale.

Object and subject of the research. Object: Industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region, the processes of their modernization of their activities through online sales and digital advertising tools. Subject: Representatives of industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region (managers, marketing specialists, IT department employees) and specialists working in the field of digital marketing.

Result and discussion The data collection process in research consists of the following steps:

- First stage: Contacting industrial enterprises and sending inquiries about their use of online sales and digital advertising tools.
- Second stage: Interviews with marketing and IT departments of industrial enterprises, obtaining detailed information about the implemented digital tools and their effectiveness.
- Third stage: Analyze the data obtained and identify the key characteristics, barriers, and opportunities of the digital transformation process.
- Stage Four: Based on the results obtained, develop proposals for industrial enterprises and recommend ways to solve problems that arise when implementing digital marketing.

The advantages of research methods include the fact that data obtained through qualitative methods provide an in-depth analysis of the research and provide a detailed picture of how digital tools are being adopted by industrial enterprises.

- Using quantitative methods, the effectiveness of online sales and digital advertising, as well as changes in export potential, are measured.
- Comparative analysis allows for comparison with experiments conducted in other regions and helps to learn from successful practices implemented globally.

The limitations of the study are that the data are focused only on industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region, which leads to the preparation of results only for regional characteristics. The success of the study depends on the honest and complete provision of information by representatives of industrial enterprises.

The research methodology allows for an in-depth study of the processes of industrial enterprises in the implementation of online sales and digital advertising tools. The approaches, methods and techniques used in the research help ensure that the results are accurate and reliable, which allows for the development of effective proposals for the digital transformation of industry in the Kashkadarya region.

This study analyzed the transformation of online sales and digital advertising in industrial enterprises of the Kashkadarya region. The main objective of the study was to study the process of digital transformation of industrial enterprises, their opportunities to increase export potential through the use of online sales and digital advertising tools. The results of the study and the discussion based on them include the following main aspects.

The use of online sales and digital advertising tools in industrial enterprises. According to the results of the study, industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region are still limited in the implementation of online sales and digital advertising tools. Most enterprises have not yet fully transitioned to digital marketing, and only some companies use online sales platforms. Digital advertising tools are used more to promote brands and general information about products.

However, the digital tools used by businesses, mainly focused on the local market and strategies aimed at operating globally, are still poorly developed. In addition, the lack of knowledge of employees in developing online sales on e-commerce platforms and social networks also poses some obstacles.

The study also examined the role of digital marketing tools in increasing export potential. The results showed that online sales and digital advertising tools create great opportunities in the process of integration with global markets. Many industrial enterprises, especially small and medium-sized enterprises, are trying to enter new markets by selling their products on online sales platforms (such as Alibaba, Amazon, or their own e-commerce sites).

However, the main conclusion from the study is that expanding export opportunities requires not only the introduction of online trading tools, but also the development of qualified personnel, a logistics system and in-depth development of digital marketing strategies to successfully trade through these platforms. Also, effective promotion should be carried out on a global scale through digital advertising, which will ensure the attraction of the right target audience and the adaptation of the product to specific market segments.

During the research on obstacles and challenges, a number of obstacles and challenges were also identified. The most important of them are the following:

- Underdeveloped technical infrastructure and network: Industrial enterprises in Kashkadarya region, especially small and medium-sized enterprises, reported a low level of necessary technical infrastructure and network connectivity, which hinders the effective use of online sales and digital advertising tools.
- Training and knowledge gap: The lack of qualified professionals in digital marketing and e-commerce, especially in small and medium-sized enterprises, is limiting the ability to fully utilize digital tools and platforms. Organizations should organize programs aimed at training employees in this area and developing digital skills.
- Not fully utilizing social media and e-commerce platforms: Industrial enterprises often use social media only for general advertising and providing product information. However, there is a significant opportunity to sell products, interact with customers, and develop a brand by operating on e-commerce platforms.

Based on the research results, the following recommendations can be made:

- Implementation of digital marketing and e-commerce systems: Industrial enterprises in Kashkadarya region should expand their online sales and digital advertising tools. This, in turn, will facilitate their integration into the global market and increase their export potential. To do this, enterprises should develop digital marketing strategies and join e-commerce platforms.
- Staff training: Training qualified specialists in digital marketing and e-commerce, especially those working in online sales and digital advertising, is essential. By organizing special trainings and courses, industrial enterprises can take advantage of all the opportunities of digital marketing.
- Adapting products to the global market: Industrial enterprises need to effectively use digital advertising tools to present their products to the global market. To successfully sell on online sales platforms, it is important to adapt the product to global requirements and market segments, as well as identify the target audience through analytical tools.

The results of the study show that industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region have the opportunity to increase their export potential by expanding online sales and digital advertising. However, for this process to be successful, it is necessary to develop technical infrastructure, personnel training, and a strategic approach. The correct use of digital marketing and e-commerce will contribute to the integration of the industry into the global market and economic growth.

Conclusion.

Conclusion: This study examined the transformation of online sales and digital advertising in industrial enterprises of the Kashkadarya region. The main objective of the study was to analyze the integration of online sales and digital marketing tools in industrial enterprises and to determine their role in increasing export potential.

The results showed that industrial enterprises in Kashkadarya region, especially small and medium-sized enterprises, are not yet fully developed in the implementation of online sales and digital advertising tools. Digital marketing tools are more focused on the local market, and the opportunities for entering the global market are still limited. In addition, the lack of technical infrastructure and human resources, as well as the uncertainty of marketing strategies, create obstacles for enterprises.

At the same time, the study also revealed important results on the positive impact of online sales and digital advertising on the integration of industrial enterprises into the global market and increasing their export potential. The effective use of digital marketing allows industrial enterprises to open new markets, promote their brand globally, and present their products to an expanded audience.

Proposals: Expand the implementation of digital marketing and e-commerce systems. It is necessary to develop digital marketing and expand e-commerce systems for industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region. This, in turn, will create opportunities for enterprises to open new export markets and enter the global market by making maximum use of digital tools.

Development of technical infrastructure. To implement the digital transformation of industrial enterprises, it is necessary to strengthen the technical infrastructure. This will allow for the transition to high-speed internet, secure payment systems, and modern e-commerce platforms.

Training and development of personnel. The marketing efficiency of industrial enterprises can be improved by increasing the number of specialists in online sales and digital marketing, as well as by training existing employees and introducing them to new digital tools. Through special training and educational programs, enterprises should familiarize their employees with modern digital technologies.

Adapting products to the global market. To successfully sell on online trading platforms, it is necessary to adapt products to the requirements of the global market. Maintaining a high level of quality of products and services, and adapting marketing strategies and communication tools to different markets will be beneficial for businesses.

Expand your social media presence. Businesses should effectively use social media not only to promote their products, but also to engage with customers, grow their brand, and build their global audience. By being active on social media and constantly updating their content, businesses can make the most of digital marketing.

Develop a digital marketing strategy. Businesses should not view digital marketing as just an advertising tool. They should develop digital marketing strategies that involve direct customer engagement, proper product segmentation, and the use of new marketing methods.

Strengthening cooperation with local government and business organizations. Cooperation between government agencies and business organizations is important in the development of digital marketing. The government should develop programs to invest in the digital economy, develop infrastructure, and support small and medium-sized businesses.

In general, the expansion of online sales and digital advertising tools for industrial enterprises in the Kashkadarya region will create new opportunities for them. For the successful implementation of this process, it is necessary to develop digital marketing, strengthen technical infrastructure, and improve personnel skills. The success of digital transformation will open up new markets for industrial enterprises, contributing to economic growth and increased export potential.

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